

TRENDS IN PCBs AND CHLORINATED PESTICIDES IN U.S. FISH AND SHELLFISH

Alan J. Mearns

Ocean Assessments Division, NOAA
Seattle, Washington 98115

ABSTRACT

Historical data on concentrations of PCBs and chlorinated pesticides in U.S. marine and estuarine fish and invertebrates have been collected, archived and analyzed to determine long-term and large-scale geographic trends and to provide a basis for improving monitoring strategies. Data have been acquired from about 20,000 samples of nearly 500 marine species surveyed over the past three decades. The approach developing this data base is described.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and chlorinated pesticides, such as aldrin, DDT, dieldrin, kepone and toxaphene, are a few of the thousands of synthetic organic chemicals that have been produced and released throughout the United States for nearly a half a century. They are toxic, long-lasting and can accumulate to hazardous levels in tissues of living organisms. Although, they have been subject to extensive research and monitoring, and have been banned or severely limited in use in the United States, they remain, today, pivotal contaminants in pollution-related resource use conflicts, resource closures and waste management decisions. In short, they don't seem to be going away fast enough.

What has been happening with these chemicals in estuarine and marine resources of the United States? Stout (1986) provides a partial answer for PCBs: the "hot spots" are cooling off possibly at the expense of contaminating formerly "clean" resources and areas. What about the others and what about PCB-contaminated organisms in areas not included in recent reviews? Indeed, what have we learned from two- to three-decades of coastal monitoring? Have past legislative mandates taken hold or not? What are the lessons for future monitoring for these and other pervasive contaminants?

To find out, a national review of trends in PCBs and chlorinated pesticides was initiated as part of the new NOAA National Status and Trends

Program (NS&TP; Ehler and Calder, 1986) by OAD's Coastal and Estuarine Assessment Branch. This paper describes that project, which is now underway, and presents a glimpse of the kind and amount of data now being examined. The emphasis here is on how a detailed review of historical pollution data is being undertaken.

2. METHODS

A pilot study for one coast was performed (Matta et al., 1986) to estimate feasibility at the national level and to develop protocols for the larger effort. These protocols are described below.

Data were taken directly from numerous published and unpublished reports, magnetic tapes and diskettes, extracted into a common format, entered into a desk-top data base management system and are now being examined for taxonomic, geographic and long-term trends according to a suite of developing criteria. To conduct the data search, individual staff members were each assigned a specific geographic area and charged with making appropriate literature searches and contacts. Published reports were identified through traditional library search methods. Personal contacts and leads to unpublished reports and data sets were identified from several existing national reviews such as NOAA's 1980-81 regional workshops on ocean pollution research (Wick et al., 1980) and monitoring (Segar, 1981). Federal, state and local agencies involved in monitoring or research were contacted directly at central and regional offices.

The goal was to obtain data on individual samples (records), with complete documentation of the location, date, depth, species, organ or tissue, size, sex, weight, number of specimens used in composites, lipid and water content, extraction and analytical methods used, references to intercalibration success and concentrations of individual contaminants. Potentially valid "data sets" were acquired, assigned a tracking code and extracted for entry into a FOCUS-based data base management system. Not all acquisitions resulted in extractable data, but were retained for future reference. Where only mean values were available (data

lost, etc.) they were so noted. The schema for the computer system was built around six inter-linked segments including: survey information; commentary text; station information; sample information; methods information; and contaminant residue data.

Data were prioritized for extraction, entry and analysis. The first priority included large-scale surveys and monitoring activities of nearly oceanic proportions (synoptically covering two or more coasts, such as Butler, 1973 and Stout, 1980). Second priority was given to synoptic large-scale regional surveys involving one coast (e.g., Giam et al., 1978) or at least several states or very-long-term monitoring data (i.e., decadal, such as MacGregor, 1974) regardless of geographic scope. Third priority was given to data which when combined with others would provide the opportunity for reconstructing geographical or long-term trends for specific species, embayments or exceptional groups of years. Extraction, entry and error and range checking was achieved according to criteria and rules outlined in a manual dedicated to the project (Buchman, 1986).

3. RESULTS

Data acquisition has exceeded expectations. At least 35,000 records have been identified that include PCB and/or chlorinated pesticide data from at least an estimated 500 species of marine invertebrates and fishes of U.S. arctic, temperate and tropical estuarine and coastal waters and the deep sea. The data come from an estimated 300-325 surveys or data sets. An interim data inventory, describing the first 217 surveys or data sets, was recently published (OAD, 1986).

Of the data identified, information from about 150 surveys or data sets, involving about 20,000 records have been extracted and/or entered into the data base. These involve approximately 450 species and most of these are fish, indicating that something on the order of one-fifth to one-quarter of the coastal U.S. ichthyofauna has been measured. To the best of our knowledge, several major national historical data sets have been completely or systematically digitized for the first time as have many state and regional data sets.

Only cursory inspections of the data have been done at this writing. For information on specific trends already identified to date, for the West Coast, the reader is referred to Matta et al (1986). From a cursory scan of the more complete data set, it appears that most of the records contain data on DDT residues, and perhaps two-thirds with PCB data. There are thousands of entries for pesticides such as aldrin, dieldrin, lindane, and chlordane at or below analytical detection limits. There are also small, geographically concentrated, sets

of samples reflecting locally-high concentrations at various sites around the country. There are hundreds of records for mirex and toxaphene, again many at or below analytical detection limits, but also some clear "hot spots" as well.

In terms of analytical quality assurance, it appears that fully 90% of the data are derived from packed-column gas chromatography and only the recent 10% from capillary columns. This raises an important question: while there is considerable opportunity to inter-compare the bulk of the past data, to what extent can it be compared to the very recent data? On the other hand, nearly one half of the records come with information confirming implementation of an inter-laboratory or inter-calibration experience, providing good opportunity for identifying inter-laboratory linkages and, if needed, the possibility of normalizing data sets. Some of these may bridge the gap between the past and new methods.

There are clearly thousands of records over long-periods of time and over large geographic areas (all coasts) for specific taxa and groups of organisms, most notably oysters, clupeid (herring-like) fishes and other small forage fish (anchovy, herring, menhaden, sardine), and popular recreational species such as striped bass. Likewise, there are historical records from remote sites and from deep-sea and oceanic organisms.

Data is abundant where we supposed it was not, such as in the upper Chesapeake, Long Island Sound, the Texas coast, and in the vicinity of Honolulu, Hawaii. Maps are being prepared to document historical spatial coverage, nationwide. Data is also abundant when we supposed it was not. As seen in Figure 1, the majority of data now entered comes from the period 1965 through 1975, with peak years producing nearly 1800 samples. These are largely the product of the National Pesticide Monitoring Program (Butler, 1973 and Butler and Schutzmann, 1978). The mid-1970's appear to be relatively poorly sampled (under 400 samples per year). Indeed, sampling effort seems to have decayed since the 60's. This is partially a consequence of our extraction priorities. A gross scan of data remaining to be entered will reverse the apparent downward trend in Figure 1; the new data is largely from state and regional authorities. The addition of data from new sampling conducted by the NS&T Program above, will markedly increase the trend toward annual densities approaching historic activity of the late 1960's.

There is even data for fish collected in the 1940's and 1950's, before the advent of recent and currently-used analytical techniques and, indeed, before the occurrence of some pesticides was even known for marine organisms. Many of these come from retrospective analyses of museum specimens (MacGregor, 1974).

4. DISCUSSION

Data extraction, entry and evaluation is far from complete, analytical quality needs to be compared for the purposes of long-term and large-scale trend assessment and many "bugs" need to be worked out of already extracted information. The "bugs" include apparent inconsistencies in sample locations, species identifications, contaminant concentrations and sampling dates. Nonetheless, it is now apparent that a huge body of historical pollution data is available that can be brought to bear toward answering some fundamental questions about pollution trends, locations and identity of historically clean and contaminated resources (for these materials) and about monitoring strategies.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This is a "people project." The work described in this report is part of an ongoing effort involving many individuals within the Ocean Assessments Division and former staff. I particularly wish to acknowledge the people who have been seeking, identifying, acquiring, processing and assessing data. These include Michael Buchman, Maggie Ernst, Sandra Golembiewska, Edward Long, Carol Ann Manen, Dr. Garry Mayer, Mary Matta, Rosemary Monahan, Kirk Van Ness, William Wert and Dr. David Young. Data extraction and entry has been a key activity and special thanks are due to Debra Simecek-Beatty and Vickey Dukes. The project would have been impossible without the support and encouragement of OAD managers Drs. Howard Harris, John Calder, Louis Butler, Charles Ehler and Andrew Robertson and editorial assistance from Gerry Arbios.

The project would be non-existent without the data collected, preserved and provided by numerous individuals and agencies. It is impossible to name them all here, but on behalf of the staff it is my pleasant duty to thank those we have recently bothered the most including: Dr. Philip Butler (EPA); Drs. John MacGregor, Robert Reid, Frank Steimle, Virginia Stout, and Jeanette Whipple (NMFS/NOAA); Librarians Bruce Keck and Martha Ballard (NOAA); Dr. Howard Metzker (USFWS); Dr. Ronald Sloan (New York Department of Environmental Conservation); Mary Jo Garreis and Dierdre Murphy (Maryland Office of Environmental Protection); Peter Phillips (California Department of Fish and Game); Dr. Irwin Haydock (Los Angeles County Sanitation Districts); and Richard Gossett (Southern California Coastal Water Research Project). Many more will be acknowledged in due course.

6. REFERENCES

- Buchman, M.F. 1986. Micro-Computer Database Operations Manual. Ocean Assessments Division, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Seattle, WA.
- Butler, P.A. 1973. Organochlorine Residues in Estuarine Mollusks, 1965-72, the National Pesticide Monitoring Program. *Pest. Mon. J.* 6(4):238-62.
- Butler, P.A. and R.L. Schutzmann, 1978. Residues of pesticides and PCBs in Estuarine Fish, National Pesticide Monitoring Program. *Pest. Mon. J.* 12(2):51-9.
- Ehler, C.N. and J.C. Calder. 1986. Measuring the Health of Coastal Waters of the USA: An Overview of NOAA's National Status and Trends Program. *Sea Technology.* 27(4):32-37.
- Giam, C.S., H.S. Chan and G.S. Neff. 1978. Phthalate ester plasticizers, DDT, DDE and polychlorinated biphenyls in biota from the Gulf of Mexico. *Mar. Poll. Bull.* 9(9):249-51.
- Matta, M., A.J. Mearns and M. F. Buchman. 1986. Trends in DDT and PCBs in U.S. West Coast Fish and Invertebrates. Ocean Assessments Division, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Seattle, WA. 95 pp.
- MacGregor, J.S. 1974. Changes in the amount and proportion of DDT and its metabolites, DDE and DDD, in the marine environment off Southern California, 1949-1972. *Fish. Bull.* 72(2):275-93.
- Ocean Assessments Division. 1986. Inventory of Chlorinated Pesticide and PCB Data for U.S. Marine and Estuarine Fish and Invertebrates. Ocean Assessments Division, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Seattle, WA. 44 pp.
- Segar, D.A. 1981. An Assessment of Great Lakes and Ocean Pollution Monitoring in the United States. Working paper No. 7 Federal Plan for Ocean Pollution Research, Development and Monitoring, FY 1981-1985. National Marine Pollution Program Office, NOAA, Rockville, MD.
- Stout, V.F. 1980. Organochlorine residues in fishes from the Northwest Atlantic Ocean and Gulf of Mexico. *Fish. Bull.* 78(1):51-58.
- Stout, V.F. 1986. What is Happening to PCBs? Elements of Effective Environmental Monitoring as Illustrated by an Analysis of PCB Trends in Terrestrial and Aquatic Organisms. PCBs in The Environment. CRC Press.
- Wick, W. et al. 1980. Report of West Coast Region Conference on Marine Pollution Problems. Portland, Oregon, June 17-19, 1980. Working paper No. 6: Federal Plan for Ocean Pollution, Research, Development and Monitoring, FY 1981-1985. National Marine Pollution Program Office, NOAA, Rockville, MD. 97 pp.

Number of samples by Year

FIGURE 1. Number of archived samples per year of chlorinated pesticides and PCBs in U.S. estuarine and marine fish and invertebrates.